

Indian Banking Structure and Nationalization of Banks

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Abstract

Entire banking institution can be included under the Indian banking system, which are providing banking services all over India. These institutions are providing different types of services to different sections in a wide geographical area according to their needs. This is a large, complex and intensive organisation which is playing an important role in the economic development of the country. In this organized and unorganized, private and social, domestic and foreign, rural and urban, modern and traditional all kinds of forms are found. In fact the Indian banking system is as diverse as its cultural and social system. The purpose of the presented research paper is to study the nationalization of Indian banks.

Key words : India, Bank, Bank Structure, Nationalization of Banks.

Although most of the banking system exist in the organized sector yet a wide and parallel banking system is active in both rural and urban areas by the names of banker, sahuakar, Mahajan shah ji, srishti Seth etc. In spite of having many defects in this organized and irregular system, this system is working in an easily accepted form.¹ Branch banking system has been prevalent since beginning for the expansion of banking services in a wide geographical area like India. The success of a bank is also considered to be the number of its branches. The total number of branches of State Bank of India and its subsidiary banks is 15,389 which is the highest for any bank.² Foreign banks are also working in the field of some specialised services. There are 36 foreign banks in India serving in specific areas like retail banking as well as foreign exchange investment portfolio management, foreign trade etc. Due to the failure of commercial and cooperative banks to meet the needs of rural areas, regional rural banks were established These regional Rural banks have come into existence under the regional rural banks act 1976. A rural bank, though a separate entity is closely linked to the commercial bank that established it and was the sponsor. It is also necessary to make the local limits within which such Regional Rural Bank can carry on its business as a branch or agency. Presently, 104 regional rural banks are functioning. Cooperative banks are formed under cooperative societies Act passed by various States. It is a three tier system with State cooperative Bank as the apex institution, Central or district cooperative Bank functions at the district level and primary credit societies are found at the village level. These banks work on the principle of cooperative as a non profit organisation. Cooperative Banks basically provide financial services for agriculture and related work in rural areas.

Historically, The banking system has a close relationship with trade and traditional industries. For a long time, banks hesitated to enter new areas. At present apart from meeting the needs of industrial finance and agriculture, banks are also providing finance to small and medium industries. Banks are actively cooperating in the development of the country by cooperating in basic industries and home finance.³After nationalization, banks are paying more attention to providing finance to the priority sectors .Along with giving loans to small traders and entrepreneurs, special schemes have also been

implemented to provide loans to agriculture, handicrafts and weaker sections. Special loan schemes are also operational for road transport drivers, professionals and self employed persons.⁴ Presently, banks are providing various services in addition to traditional banking activities. For this, the government has also issued guidelines to encourage them to diversify. Commercial banks provide direct and indirect finance services to the agricultural sector under self finance and refinance schemes.

In the year 2011-12 finance of rupees 2,62,129 crores was made available for agriculture and allied activities. Under the kisan credit card scheme a total of rupees 52,7,052 financial facilities have been provided through 10,7,836 lakh kisan credit card till March 31-10-2012. Announced in the year 2008 for the benefit of small and marginal farmers rupees 70, 000 Gramin bank loan weaver scheme was also a historic step in the direction of agricultural finance. Based on the guidelines announced by the RBI in the year 2000 commercial banks have done commendable work in the direction of credit achievement to SMEs.⁵ All the big banks are providing this facility at a competitive rate through their separate departments. Through SELF HELP GROUPS this section is getting financial facilities from commercial banks and regional rural banks. Commercial banks make separate financing arrangement for small and medium enterprises, which can be self funded and refinanced by SIDBI.

Before nationalization only 98,536 branches of commercial banks are working in the country. In which there are 48,982 branches of nationalized banks and 18,992 branches of State Bank group and 16,572 branches of regional the ruler banks. Commercial banks have done a commendable job in mobilizing savings.

At the end of June 1969, where the deposits of banks were rupees 4,646 crores, which increased to rupees 64,77,240 crores till December 28 2012.

Along with bank deposits, there has been a continuous expansion in bank credit. In June 1969 the total credit amount of scheduled banks was around rupees 3,600 crores which increased to rupees 50,27,210 crores by December 2012.

After the economic liberalization policy of 1991, due to the possibility of competition from private banks there was deep reforms in the working of public sector banks. Banks got saturation and according to the RULE OF GAME they understood the importance of GOOD CORPORATE GOVERNANCE in maintaining public confidence in a healthy competitive environment. It is possible to obtain funds from the public for the promotion of interest of all the stakeholders and development of the banking system only through GOOD CORPORATE GOVERNANCE, for this measures like increasing public participation, reducing government ownership, making it possible for banks to reach the primary market and qualitative improvement in management of banks were taken.⁶ All banks in their annual reports while mentioning the steps taken towards the development of corporate governance are also mentioning the efforts made in past relating to the compliance of corporate governance.⁷

With the aim of providing the benefit of banking facility to every person of the society, the target is to include the last person of the society in the banking system. All banks are encouraging to open accounts with zero balance facility through NO FRILL ACCOUNT Under this, an open invitation is being given by the bank to all students, farmers, rural artisans, unorganized workers, in which there is facility to open an account with minimum formalities.⁸

When the government takes over the ownership of an industry or business, then the action is called nationalization.

In this system, authority of the concerned industry comes into the hands of the government, it's operation is arranged by the government and the policies related to it are also determined by the government.⁹

Thus, on nationalization, the ownership, policy making, operation and control etc. of an industry come into the hands of the government. Social control of banks means that the control of the society

on their activities. In simple words ,we can say that the control of the society on the bank is a symbol of social control.

In nationalization coordination, operation and control is done by the government and the banks themselves implement national policies under social control.

In short, social control is such a system through which without nationalizing the banks, the credit policy and functioning of the banks can be determined in such a way that the resources of the banks can be used according to the national interest. Most of the resources of the commercial banks are receive from the deposits of the general public therefore, it is the duty of the government to control the policies of the banks in the social interest from the point of view of the proper use of their funds.

The capital of innumerable individuals of the society is deposited in the banks, therefore it is necessary to use that capital for the maximum benefit of the society.¹⁰To do this, social control over bank policies becomes necessary. The main objective of nationalization of banks is to awaken public confidence in the banking system. There is no question of failure of nationalized banks. That's why people's deposits are completely safe in them. To do this it becomes necessary to have social control over the policies of the bank.

Conclusion

In this way, there are some special reasons in the nationalization of banks, as a result of which some public sector banks have suffered losses. For example, the Harshad Mehta stock market scam of 1992 was also the reason for the losses of some public sector banks and some foreign banks. Thus, in the context of nationalization of banks, if some reform measures are not taken soon, as a result, the value of savings and credit assigned to these banks will vanish further and this will affect the confidence of depositors and investors.

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